

A Positive Effect of Nanotechnology On Global Warming & Climate Change

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Introductions to Nano science and Nanotechnology

Nanoscience and nanotechnology have made enormous advances in recent decades, and their impact on every sector has been widely recognized across the globe. As a result, their strategic position has already been established in the twenty first century. The study nanomaterial's and nanostructures is a relatively new discipline with several compliments. Nanomaterial's and nanostructures are crucial in the creation of Nano science and nano technology applications such as information and procedures, energy sources, the environment health, and medicinal treatments. Most countries are investing significantly in the study of nanomaterial's and nanostructures, such as the advancement of Nano science and nanotechnology Nano electronic technologies and devices, nano or micro fabrication techniques, Nano biotechnology, Nano medical Diagnosis techniques and nano environmental monitoring and treatment techniques. The continuance of indepth research on nanomaterial's and nanostructures is vitally crucial. Furthermore, the (indepth) study of nanomaterial and nanostructures is a valuable source for developing new ideas, methodologies, and procedures, possibly leading to breakthroughs in major scientific challenges. At the same time, the nanomaterial market is a native power for nanomaterial development.

Introduction of Nanomaterials

Nanomaterials are essential components of nanoscience and nanotechnology. Nanostructure science and technology is a large and multidisciplinary field of study and development that has grown rapidly in recent years across the globe. It has the potential to change the way materials and products are generated as well as the range and kind of functions that maybe accessible. Current in semiconductors may be carried by the flow of electrons or the movement of positively charged holes in the material's electron structure. Nanomaterials with diameters ranging from 1 to 20 nm have emerged as a prominent multidisciplinary area of research interest in the last decade, with the promise for wide-reaching industrial, biological, and electrical applications. Surfaces and interfaces are critical in nanomaterials, although in bulk materials, only a tiny number of atoms will be at or near a surface or interface. The tiny feature size of nanomaterials assures that many atoms, potential 50% or more in certain situations, will be near the interfaces. Surfaces features such as energy levels, electrical structure, and reactivity, may vary significantly from internal states, resulting in quite distinct material properties. Nanocapsules and nanodevices have the potential to open up new avenues for medication delivery, gene therapy, and medical diagnostics. Carbon nanotubes are utilised as reinforcing particles in nanocomposites, but they also have a

wide range of additional uses. They may serve as the foundation for a new age of electrical devices that are smaller and more powerful than bulk materials. Carbon nanotubes have previously been used to build a nanocomputer. Materials with nanometer-scale dimensions have different characteristics than bulk materials.

When semiconductor materials are shrunk to the nanoscale, their physical and chemical characteristics change dramatically, resulting in unique features owing to their enormous surface area or quantum size effect. The semiconductor's conductivity and optical characteristics (absorption coefficient and refractive index) may be changed. Semiconductor nanomaterials and devices are still in the research stage, but they have the potential to be used in a variety of fields, including solar cells, nanoscale electronic devices, light emitting diodes, laser technology, waveguide, chemical and biosensors, packaging films, super absorbents, amour components, automobile parts, and catalysts. Semiconductor devices include numerous types of transistors, solar cells, various types of diodes such as light emitting diodes, silicon-controlled rectifiers, and digital and analogue integrated circuits. Some semiconductor nanomaterials, such as Si, Ge, GaAs, AlGaAs, InP, InGaAs, GaN, AlGaN, SiC, ZnS, ZnSe, AlIn, GaP, CdSe, CdS, and HgCdTe have extensive applications in computers, palm pilots, laptops, cell phones, pagers, CD players,

TV remotes mobile terminals, satellite dishes, fibre networks.

History of Nanomaterials

Michael Faraday created colloidal gold particles in 1857, which was one of the earliest scientific reports. Nanostructured catalysts have also been studied for more than 70 years by the early 1940s precipitated and fumed silica nanoparticles were being made and commercialized in the United States and Germany as ultrafine carbon black alternatives for rubber re-enforcements. Nanosized

Classification of Nanomaterials

Nanomaterials are exceedingly tiny, with at least one dimension of 100 nm or less. Nanomaterials might be one dimension (for example, surface films), two dimensions (for example, strands or fibres), or three dimensions (eg. particles). They may be solitary, fused, aggregated, or agglomerated, and, can have spherical, tubular, or irregular morphologies. Nanotubes, dendrimers, quantum dots, and fullerenes are examples of common

amorphous silica particles have found widespread use in a wide range of everyday consumer items, including nondairy coffee creamer, automotive tyres, optical fibres, and catalytic supports. Metallic nanopowders for magnetic recording cassettes were created in the 1960s and 1970s. Granqvist and Buhrman reported nanocrystals made using the increasingly standard inert gas evaporation process for the first time in 1976. It was recently discovered that Maya blue paint is a nanostructured hybrid material.

Fig. 1: Nanomaterial (Carbon nanotube)

Nano materials. Nanomaterials have uses in the realm of nanotechnology and exhibit physical and chemical properties that vary from ordinary substances (i.e., silver nano, carbon nanotube, fullerene, photo catalyst, carbon nano, silica). Siegel classifies nanostructured materials as zero-dimensional, one-dimensional, two-dimensional, and three-dimensional nanostructures. Nanomaterials are defined as

materials with ultrafine grain sizes (50 nm or dimensionality confined to 50 nm). According to Richard W. Siegel, nanomaterials may be generated with several modulation dimensionalities: zero (atomic clusters, filaments, and cluster assemblies), one (multilayers), two (ultrafine-grained over layers or buried layers), and three (nanophase materials consisting of equiaxed nanometer sized grains) (**Fig 2**).

Fig.2: Classification of Nanomaterials (a) 0D spheres and clusters; (b) 1D nanofibers, Nano-wires, and nanorods; (c) 2D, nanofilms, nanoplates, and networks; (d) 3D nanomaterials

Types of Nanomaterials

Current Nanoparticles (NPs) and Nano Semiconductor Materials (NSM) may be classified under four material groups. There are two types of carbon based nanomaterials based nanomaterials:

(i) carbon-based nanomaterials: These NMs often include carbon and have geometries such as hollow tubes, ellipsoids, or spheres. Carbon-based NMs include fullerenes (C₆₀), carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon nanofibers, and carbon black, grapheme (Gr), and carbon onions. These carbon-based compounds are manufactured via laser ablation, are discharge,

and chemical vapour deposition (CVD) (except carbon black).

(ii) Metal and metal oxide NPs and NSMs are examples of inorganic-based nanomaterials. These NMs may be used to make metals like Au or Ag NPs, metal oxides like TiO₂ and ZnO Nanoparticles, and semiconductors like silicon and ceramics.

(iii) Organic-based nanomaterials: These are NMs derived primarily from organic matter, as opposed to carbon- or inorganic-based NMs. The Use of Non-covalent (weak) interactions for molecular self- assembly and design aids in the transformation of organic NMs into desirable structures such as dendrimers, micelles, liposomes, and polymer NPs.

(iv) Nanomaterials based on composites: Composite NMs are multiphase NPs and NSMs with one phase on the nanoscale dimension that may combine NPs with other NPs or NPs with bigger or bulk- type materials (e.g., hybrid nanofibers) or more intricate structures (e.g., metal organic frame works). The composites may be made up of any combination of carbon-based, metal-based, or organic- based NMs and metal, ceramic, or polymer bulk components.

Positive Effects of Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology improves the strength of numerous materials and devices while also increasing the efficiency of monitoring devices, using less energy, reducing material waste, preventing toxicity, environmental pollution cleanup, and renewable energy generation.

While these are seen to be favourable effects of nanotechnology. The utilization of nanomaterials and nanoparticles may also result in considerable resource savings and increased efficiency in industrial and energy-related applications. Nanotechnology as the potential to provide Economic, social, and environmental advantages. It has the ability to help lessen the human impact on the environment by addressing issues like as energy usage, pollution, and green gas emissions. Nanotechnology has the possibility of solving the twenty-first century's global concerns, such as supplying alternative energy, defending the human right to clean water, assuring wildlife protection, cleaning up brown fields, and lowering global disease load. It haste potential to provide major environmental advantages, such as:

- cleaner and more efficient industrial processes
- Improved detection and elimination of pollutants through increasing air,water, and soil quality

High precision manufacturing via waste reduction...

Clean ample electricity through highly efficient solar cells

Reduction in the demand for huge industrial units due to the removal of greenhouse gases and other pollutants from the environment

Repairing environmental damage

Nanoscale products that utilize grapheme in commercial or research applications might assist the environment in numerous ways; Graphene-based nanocomposites lower aircraft weight by replacing standard metals and composites, and the weight savings result in a thousand tones of petroleum saved. Metal meshes surrounding the fuselage of an aircraft may be replaced by grapheme thin films or grapheme buck sheets.

To avoid the direct and indirect consequences of lightning strikes The outstanding features of grapheme improve the efficiency of modern renewable energy processes, such as decreasing the weight of wind turbine blades and enhancing energy conversion efficiency.

Energy Consumption: By incorporating grapheme into a coating material, just one layer is required, eliminating the requirement for a multifunctional film coating. A graphene- based coating has two applications: it may be applied to wind turbine blades or the body of an aircraft, It reduces weight while enhancing efficiency.

Material Cost Savings: Novel breakthroughs in nanotechnology will reduce the cost of alternative energy methods such as hybrid autos.

Less Raw Material Waste: Large sample testing will be done on a smaller scale, and raw material consumption will become more efficient. Nanoscale chemical reagents (or catalysts)n speed up chemical processes and improve their overall efficiency.

Environmental Protection and Monitoring: A detector was developed using sophisticated nanotechnology to detect a radioactive leak at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant quicker and more accurately. This is one of Washington's finest radiation detectors and can detect even the smallest amount of radiation.

Clean and inexpensive energy: When it comes to turning sunshine into power, prototype solar panels using nanotechnology outperform regular designs. Nanotechnology is used in batteries, and nanoparticles may enhance hydrogen storage materials and fuel cell catalysts. Nanotechnology may improve energy production conversion and storage by generating larger surface area and lighter storage units for fuel cells, solar cells,

thermo-to- electric, biomass energy, hydrogen storage, secondary batteries, super- capacitors, and thermal storage fluids.

Protect in the human right to safe drinking water: Because of its speedy and low-cost contaminant identification nanotechnology enables low- cost water filtration. Magnetic interactions with ultra- small rust may aid in the removal of arsenic from drinking water. Nanotechnology may potentially enhance monitoring of air and water quality by inventing more sensitive detection systems capable of measuring a wide variety of pollutants and harmful chemicals at the same time. Rapid detection enables rapid action, limiting damage and lowering repair costs.

Environmental Progress and Pollution Reduction: Lighter automobiles and machines that use less fuel; alternative fuel and energy sources; and materials that detect and remove environmental toxins all seem to be feasible. The University College Dublin (UCD) Center for Bio- Nano Interactions (CBNI) investigates the impact of nanoparticles dispersed in the environment, where decaying plant and animal matter transforms into natural organic matter, typically composed of polysaccharides, and investigates how this interaction affects organic stability, dispersability, environmental fate, and behaviour.

Global Disease Burden Reduction: Personal well-being will grow globally as health care improves via better diagnosis and treatment. Economic Crisis Mitigation Investment in Nanotechnology will encourage economic growth, which will assist the development of auxiliary sectors such as product marketing, waste recycling and disposal, and intellectual property and liability disputes.

Effect of Nanotechnology on Global Warming Global Warming Effect

Global Warming is the world's most recent crisis. All governments and organizations in developed and developing nations are working to minimize it. Global warming refers to the exceptionally fast rise in the Earth's average surface temperature over the last century, which is mostly attributable to green-house gases emitted by humans who use fossil fuels. Over the previous century the global average surface temperature has risen by 0.6 to 1.0 degrees Celsius. This is due to the greenhouse effect. Nearly 30% of incoming sun radiations are reflected back to space from the outer side of the earth's atmosphere, while the 70% enters the earth's atmosphere. A fraction of these radiations (visible light spectrum) is absorbed by the

Earth, and the earth re-radiate this absorbed energy in the form of heat i.e., infrared radiations.

Greenhouse gases including carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxide, methane, fluorinated gases, and water vapour collect heat from infrared radiations and block its departure from the atmosphere, As a result, infrared radiations persist in the earth's atmosphere for an extended period of time, causing the earth's surface temperature to rise. Carbon dioxide emissions are a major contributor to global warming. According to several assessments, the average surface temperature of the Earth might increase by 2°C to 5°C by the end of the twenty-first century.

Climate Change Effect

Climate change induced by greenhouse gases, mostly carbon dioxide (CO₂) created from the combustion of fossil fuels, has caused significant changes in ecosystems and resulted in roughly 150,000 more fatalities per year. This increase is mostly due to the unsustainable use of fossil fuels and changes in land use. Our reliance on fossil fuels is a major contributor to global warming; this is one of the most pressing environmental issues in the near future. Automobiles and industry have recently contributed to a significant rise in greenhouse gases, notably carbon dioxide. Carbon dioxide levels in the atmosphere are 387 parts per million (ppm), over 40% higher since the industrial revolution, according to the United States National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). The burning of fossil fuels such as oil, gas, and coal is the major source of carbon dioxide emissions in the atmosphere. Greenhouse gases have irreversible effects on the ozone layer, the environment, and human health. Global warming has become a global concern that requires prompt response from all governments. To overcome this problem, many techniques might be used:

1. Reduce energy usage while improving the efficiency of current technology.
2. Reduce the use of fossil fuels in autos and industry and replace them with re-neweable energy sources.
3. Participate in carbon management, which entails separating and transforming carbon into valuable goods.

There are several techniques to reduce energy usage and, as a result, greenhouse gas emissions in many important domains. Nanotechnology has had a significant influence on our lives by offering a feasible alternative to fossil fuels and thereby lowering greenhouse gas emissions.

Transportation and industry are the two largest sources of greenhouse gases in the environment. The current pace of global warming may harm our planet in the future. The latter two decades of the twentieth century were the warmest in 400 years. Climate change has occurred on Earth in the past, but present climate change is faster and damaging. Nanotechnology tackles the problem of global warming by reducing the use of fossil fuels, reducing energy consumption, and improving the efficiency of current renewable energy technologies.

Conclusion

Nanotechnology is a multidisciplinary method that necessitates extensive cross-sector cooperation among university researchers, businesses and government. While nanomaterials may assist clean up certain environmental debris, they can also pollute the environment in other ways. Choosing the correct nanoscale materials is one of the most important aspects for the future of nanotechnology. The Nanotechnology will continue to evolve, help society, and enhance the environment in a variety of ways. Nanomaterials will improve product functionality, weight savings, energy usage, and environmental sustainability. Nanotechnology has the ability to drastically reduce greenhouse gas emissions and thereby mitigate global warming. The current pace of global warming may harm our planet in the future. The latter two decades of the twentieth century were the warmest in 400 years. Climate change has occurred on Earth in the past, but present climate change is more fast and damaging. Nanotechnology tackles the problem of global warming by reducing the use of fossil fuels, reducing energy consumption, and improving the efficiency of current renewable energy technologies.

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